

A Comparative LCA of Thermal and Mechanical Activation in Clay Material Processing

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Abstract. This study compares the environmental impacts of two clay activation technologies – flash calciner (thermal) and agitated bead mill (mechanical) – using clays from Brazil and Denmark as Supplementary Cementitious Materials (SCMs) for cement production. A cradle-to-gate life cycle assessment (LCA) based on openLCA software, Ecoinvent database, and industrial data was utilized to evaluate the environmental impacts to produce one kilogram of activated clay. Global warming potential (GWP, kg CO₂-eq) was the primary impact category for the LCA study since it is a key driver of climate change. Moreover, a sensitivity analysis was carried out to evaluate the impact of the energy mix on the LCA outcome. For the assessed clays, the LCA shows that thermal activation yields in average 34% greater CO₂ emissions than that from mechanical activation; despite the latter having an average of 26% higher total energy consumption against thermal activation. Since both technologies require similar energy for drying the clay's moisture, the energy difference from the processes stems primarily from the agitated bead mill's higher power demand. The sensitivity analysis shows that when electricity is sourced mainly from fossil fuels, CO₂ emissions from mechanical activation can exceed those of thermal activation. Additionally, an analysis of energy consumption and operating costs reveals that, under current energy pricing, flash calcination is more cost-effective than mechanical activation. Overall, this study underscores the importance of factors such as clay composition, moisture content, and regional energy mix in assessing the environmental and economic performance of activated clays. While both activation methods present trade-offs, the high electricity demand of current mechanical activation process highlights the need for the development of more energy-efficient activation technologies that help produce more sustainable SCMs for composite cement production.

Keywords: Clays; Life Cycle Assessment; Mechanical activation; Thermal activation.

1 Introduction

Concrete is a fundamental material in modern infrastructure worldwide, with global production estimated in 2020 at approximately 14 billion m³ annually [1,2]. As a crucial component of the construction industry, Portland cement (PC) has long been used as a hydraulic binder in concrete mixtures [1,3]. However, the production of PC is a significant source of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, contributing to global climate change. As a result, efforts have been made to reduce these emissions, including the partial replacement of PC with supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs), which can

improve the strength performance and durability of concrete structures while simultaneously lowering their environmental impact [4-6].

Within the field of SCMs, activated clays are gaining increased attention as potential SCMs due to the widespread availability of clay deposits worldwide [5-8]. Natural clays exhibit low pozzolanic activity, which are enhanced through activation processes [9]. The most common activation method is thermal activation, also known as calcination, where the material is heated to temperatures between 500°C and 900°C, depending on the optimal dehydroxylation temperature of the clay mineral [10,11]. Thermal activation has been developed to an industrial scale (TRL 8-9), with technologies such as soak and flash calciners available [10,12]. However, recent studies suggest that thermal activation may be limited, particularly for 2:1 mineral clays or low-grade kaolinite clays, due to the recrystallization of non-reactive aluminosilicate phases, such as spinel and cristobalite, which can reduce the overall pozzolanic activity [13,14]. Consequently, alternative methods like mechanical activation have been explored in recent years [15]. Mechanical activation involves altering the structure and bonding of the material through intense grinding, which can break or lengthen atomic bonds and disrupt the material's chemical cohesion [16,17]. Additionally, it operates at lower temperatures, reducing heat consumption and avoiding carbon emissions from calcination [18,19]. Although mechanical activation can be considered a promising alternative for clay activation, its industrial technological readiness remains at the development stage (TRL 4-5). Among available technologies, dry agitated bead mills currently offer the highest energy intensity (300 kW/m³), significantly surpassing traditional ball mills (20 kW/m³), making them more suitable for large-scale cement production [19-21].

This paper presents a life cycle assessment (LCA) of two naturally quarried clays from deposits in Brazil and Denmark, activated using flash calcination (thermal) and agitated bead mill (mechanical) at cement plants located near their clay pits. LCA is widely used to evaluate the environmental performance of SCMs in cement production, particularly to quantify the reduction in pollutants and energy consumption when clinker is replaced by supplementary cementitious materials [22-25]. Such assessments provide insights into the eco-efficiency of cementitious materials and their potential benefits in terms of environmental and human health impacts [25].

The primary objective of this study is to assess the environmental impacts, energy consumption, and operating costs based on their life cycle inputs for each clay. A secondary objective by comparing the environmental effects of each activation method, is to help identify the key environmental hotspots and suggest more cost/energy-efficient and sustainable solutions; providing objective data that improve understanding on the environmental implications of using activated clays in cement production. For the analysis, activation under (a) flash calcination is modelled with data from industrial plants processing and using their corresponding regional operating conditions, and (b) mechanical activation is modelled based on data extrapolated from lab-pilot tests and four power intensity scenarios ranging from 382.5 to 585 KWh/t [19-21]. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first study to compare the environmental impacts of thermal and mechanical activation for two clay sources.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

This study investigates two naturally quarried clays from distinct regions: C1 from Brazil and C2 from Denmark. Their chemical and mineralogical compositions are summarized in Table 1 and 2, respectively.

Table 1. Chemical oxide composition and loss of ignition (LOI) determined by XRF for raw C1 and C2 clay.

	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	K ₂ O	Na ₂ O	SrO	SO ₃	Other	LOI
C1	70.20	16.94	4.70	0.03	0.00	0.26	0.00	0.01	0.03	1.35	6.48
C2	57.22	18.16	8.38	0.86	2.87	2.57	1.52	0.04	1.10	1.11	6.26

The primary oxides present in both clays are SiO₂, Al₂O₃, and Fe₂O₃, with minor metal and alkali oxides detected. Both clays exhibit a SiO₂/Al₂O₃ ratio of approximately 3 and a LOI of less than 10%, indicating their classification as either 2:1 mineral clays (characterized by two silica sheets and one alumina sheet) or clays with high impurity content, such as quartz (SiO₂) [9,26]. Notably, C2 contains significant amounts of MgO and alkalis (Na₂O and K₂O), commonly associated with smectites.

Table 2. Mineralogical composition determined by XRD for raw C1 and C2 clay.

Clays	Predominant minerals (wt %)
C1	Kaolinite (48.6%), Quartz (48%), Hematite (3.4%)
C2	Montmorillonite (82%), Quartz (16%), Hematite (2%)

Mineralogical analysis reveals that C1 is predominantly kaolinite, comprising over 40% of its composition, alongside significant quartz content, correlating with its higher SiO₂ levels presented in Table 1. In contrast, C2 is rich in montmorillonite, a 2:1 type mineral clay, consistent with its chemical composition indicating smectite characteristics.

Finally, moisture content measurements revealed notable differences between the two clays as received from the quarries: C1 had an initial moisture content of 8.4%, whereas C2 exhibited a significantly higher moisture content of 25.3%.

2.2 Methods

Following to ISO14044 standards [27], an LCA study comprises four distinct phases: (1) Goal and Scope Definition, (2) Life Cycle Inventory Analysis, (3) Life Cycle Impact Assessment, and (4) Interpretation. For this study, the LCA was conducted using the software openLCA, and the phases are detailed as follows.

Goal and scope. The goal of this study is to assess and compare the environmental impacts of two clay activation technologies – flash calciner (thermal) and agitated bead mill (mechanical) – when using clays from Brazil (C1) and Denmark (C2) as Supplementary Cementitious Materials (SCMs) in cement production. Following the widely

accepted cradle-to-gate approach for building materials [1,3], the LCA includes raw material extraction, preprocessing, fuel and electricity use, transportation, clay activation, and process emissions (Fig. 1).

Flash calcination is a well-established technology for clay activation with defined heat and power demand [10,12], while mechanical activation still needs further development and market diffusion [19-21]. For both technologies, the heat required for clay drying is equivalent; however, the efficient power intensity needed to mechanically activate each clay is still unknown. Thus, for the agitated bead mill's electrical demand, four power intensity scenarios are considered based on previous lab-pilot scale data [19-21]: (1) Low – “L” (382.5 KWh/t), (2) Medium– “M” (450 KWh/t), (3) High – “H” (518 KWh/t), and (4) Higher – “H+”(585 KWh/t).

Data collection and calculations are standardized to a functional unit of 1 kg of activated clay. This choice reflects common practices for SCMs [1, 25, 28], which are typically sold in bags and measured in kilograms or tons. The functional unit serves as a consistent basis for comparing the inputs, outputs, and environmental impacts of the two activation technologies.

Fig. 1. System boundary for the cradle-to-gate LCA study on thermal (TA) and mechanical (MA) activation technologies.

Notably, the boundary excludes mixing with cement, packaging, waste treatment, material use, and final disposal, due to methodological constraints and the lack of defined service life or disposal alternatives for activated clay blends. Post-production stages are also omitted, as all mixes are assumed to have equivalent service life and end-of-life treatment.

The geographical scope covers two regions: Denmark and Brazil, where the clay pits and their corresponding cement plants are located. The analyses are based on available data from 2024 (i.e. electricity, fuel usage, distance from clay pit to the plant). Additionally, a cut-off model was applied to exclude processes with minimal environmental impact.

Data inventory. The Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) includes all inputs, outputs, energy consumption and emissions related data to make the functional unit of the product within the system boundary investigated [27,29]. For this study, data was gathered for

all relevant inputs—including raw materials, power, fuel, and transportation—and outputs, i.e. activated clay and emissions related to the clay activation process.

The inventory relies on primary data from industrial-scale flash clay calciner units for thermal activation (TA) and extrapolated lab-pilot scale data for mechanical activation (MA) scenarios (L, M, H, H⁺). Transport distances between clay pits and cement plants were included. Background system data were sourced from the Ecoinvent database, while unavailable data was supplemented using statistical and environmental reports referenced were corresponding.

Tables 3 and 4 summarize the input and output inventory data for producing 1 kg of activated C1 and C2 clay, respectively. The data compare TA with four MA power intensity scenarios, considering the energy mixes of plants in Brazil and Denmark.

Table 3. C1 data inventory (context region: Brazil).

	TA	MA			
		L	M	H	H ⁺
Inputs					
Clay (kg)			1.2		
Electricity (kWh)	0.01553	0.383	0.450	0.518	0.585
Natural gas (kg)	0.0297	0.00528	0.00528	0.00528	0.00528
Transport (kg.km)			201.6		
Outputs					
Activated clay (kg)			1		
CO ₂ (kg)	0.079976	0.01421	0.01421	0.01421	0.01421
N ₂ O (kg)	1.42E-07	2.53E-08	2.53E-08	2.53E-08	2.53E-08
CH ₄ (kg)	7.12E-06	1.26E-06	1.26E-06	1.26E-06	1.26E-06
Water (m ³)			0.0002		

Table 4. C2 data inventory (context region: Denmark)

	TA	MA			
		L	M	H	H ⁺
Inputs					
Clay (kg)			1.38		
Electricity (kWh)	0.02139	0.383	0.450	0.518	0.585
Natural gas (kg)	0.03522	0.0158	0.0158	0.0158	0.0158
Transport (kg.km)			357.4		
Outputs					
Activated clay (kg)			1		
CO ₂ (kg)	0.09484	0.0425	0.01421	0.0425	0.0425
N ₂ O (kg)	1.69E-07	7.58E-08	2.53E-08	7.58E-08	7.58E-08
CH ₄ (kg)	8.45E-06	3.79E-06	1.26E-06	3.79E-06	3.79E-06
Water (m ³)			0.00038		

Impact Assessment method. This study used openLCA software and the Ecoinvent “cut off” model [30]. Environmental impacts were evaluated based on the inputs and outputs identified in the inventory. Following a preliminary assessment (not presented in this paper), the IPCC 2013 method was selected as the most suitable for evaluating climate change-related impacts, specifically global warming potential, for all scenarios.

Interpretation. The LCA results were analyzed and interpreted to understand the environmental hotspots, identify the significant contributors to the major global impacts, and evaluate the influence on the source and costs of the energy mixes to the overall environmental and economic performance of the clay activations methods.

The IPCC2013 assessment and its interpretation are analyzed in the Results and Discussion section.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 IPCC 2013 assessment

Fig. 2 presents the results from the IPCC 2013 assessment of climate change, expressed as GWP (kg CO₂-eq) per 1 kg of activated clay, for the TA and MA scenarios (L, M, H, H+) of (a) C1 and (b) C2.

Overall, C1 (Fig. 2a) exhibits CO₂ emissions lower than C2 (Fig. 2b). This difference is likely due to variations in mineralogical composition, moisture content, and electricity mix. C1 is primarily composed of kaolinite (a 1:1 mineral clay) and has a moisture content of 8.4%. In contrast, C2 is primarily composed of montmorillonite (a 2:1 mineral clay) and has a moisture content of 25.3%. Kaolinite clays generally require less energy, fuel consumption, and temperatures for dehydroxylation. Conversely, montmorillonite clays need higher dehydroxylation temperatures, fuel consumption, and overall energy demand [13, 14]. Additionally, as for drying energy, the higher moisture content of C2 requires greater thermal energy for drying than from C1, further increasing the gap in total energy consumption between clays.

The electricity mix of the clay’s region plays a significant role: for C1, Brazil’s electricity is composed of 91% renewables (primarily hydro, followed by wind and solar) and 9% fossil fuels (mainly natural gas) [31]. In comparison, for C2, Denmark’s electricity mix is 80% renewables (dominated by wind, followed by solar and biomass) and 20% fossil fuels (primarily natural gas) [32].

The IPCC 2013 results indicate that TA generates higher CO₂-eq emissions than all MA scenarios for both clays. This difference is more pronounced for C1 (Fig. 2a) than C2 (Fig. 2b). In general, higher CO₂ emissions are directly linked to increased fuel usage. However, the higher electrical power required for MA also contributes to a greater CO₂ impact. To better understand the factors driving the total CO₂ footprint, a contribution analysis is presented in the following section.

Fig. 2. IPCC2013 assessment of climate change expressed as kg CO₂eq/kg activated clay for TA and MA scenarios (L, M, H, H+) of (a) C1 and (b) C2.

3.2 Contribution analysis per activity on the total CO₂-eq

Fig. 3 presents the contribution analysis for the GWP impact category (kg CO₂-eq), comparing TA clay with two MA scenarios (L and H+). The analysis is shown for (a) C1 and (b) C2.

The contribution analysis considers the four key input activities based on the data inventory: (1) clay quarrying at the pit, (2) transport from the pit to the cement plant, (3) the thermal and (4) electrical energy required for processing and activation of the clays at the plant.

Fig. 3. Contribution analysis for the GWP impact category (kg CO₂-eq) for TA, and MA-L, MA-H+ scenarios of (a) C1 and (b) C2.

Fig. 3a shows that the largest contributor to CO₂ emissions for C1 processing under TA is natural gas (72.2% of the total footprint – resulting from clay drying and dehydroxylating). This is followed by transport (20.31%), quarrying (7.3%) and grinding the clay (0.3%). The high contribution from natural gas arises from the fuel required for drying and dehydroxylating the clay.

For the MA scenarios in Fig. 3a, the MA-L scenario shows that transport is the largest contributor to CO₂ emissions (42.4%). This is due to the fossil fuels used by trucks, the distance traveled, and the transport method. The second largest contributor is thermal energy for drying the clay (22.1%) followed by electricity for mechanical activation (15.8%) and quarrying the kaolinitic clay (14.93%). In the MA-H⁺ scenario, transport remains the largest contributor (39.1%), followed by natural gas for drying (24.7%), electricity for activation (22.4%), and quarrying (13.8%).

For C2, Fig. 3b shows that the largest contributor to CO₂ emissions for C2 processing under TA is again natural gas (50.4%), though at a reduced level, followed by transport (25.3%), quarrying (23.4%), and electricity (1%). Compared to C1 in Fig. 3a, the contribution from natural gas is lower, while quarrying has increased significantly. This is due to the higher energy required to quarry montmorillonite clay. Transport has also slightly increased due to the larger distance between the clay pit and the plant.

For the MA C2 scenarios in Fig. 3b, the MA-L scenario shows transport as the largest contributor of CO₂ emissions (31.1%), followed by quarrying (28.8%), natural gas for drying (24.63%), and electricity for activation (15.4%). Similarly, in the MA-H⁺ scenario, the order of contributions remains the same, with transport (29.1%) as the highest, followed by quarrying (26.9%), natural gas (25.2%), and electricity for activation (18.73%). The contribution from quarrying is notably higher for C2 compared to C1 due to the differences in clay composition, while the CO₂ footprint from electricity consumption is the lowest contributor in both mechanically activated scenarios.

Since quarrying, transport from the clay pit to the plant, fuel usage (primarily natural gas in both plants), and the amount of heat required to dry the clay are the same across activation methods, the only variation among the scenarios lies in the electricity demand. Therefore, a further analysis of the influence of the electricity source was conducted.

3.3 Influence of electricity sources on the total CO₂ impact

Fig. 4a compares the Global Warming Potential (GWP) impact (kg CO₂/kg of activated clay) and electrical power consumption (kWh/kg) for C1 under TA and MA scenarios (L, M, H, H⁺) across three electricity mix simulated cases: (1) the baseline Brazilian electricity mix, consisting of 91% renewables and 9% fossil fuels; (2) an electricity mix with 75% renewables and 25% non-renewables; and (3) an electricity mix with 25% renewables and 75% non-renewables. For TA, the impact is barely noticeable, as electricity consumption is quite low (around 0.015 kWh/kg); consequently, deviations in the electricity mix result in changes that are two orders of magnitude smaller and can be considered negligible.

The results presented in Fig.4a show that Case (1) leads to the lowest environmental CO₂ impact, regardless of power intensity. Compared to the flash calciner, which shows lower power consumption, the CO₂ impact is higher due to the fossil fuels used for dehydroxylation. Case (2) is the next best option, with also a high proportion of renewable energy, leading to lower CO₂ emissions than the flash calciner. However, Case (3), with 75% non-renewable energy, results in higher CO₂ emissions for MA cases M, H, and H⁺ than the flash calciner.

Fig. 4b presents a similar comparison for the C2, with TA and MA scenarios (L, M, H, H⁺) under the three electricity mix simulated cases: (1) the baseline Danish

electricity mix, consisting of 80% renewables and 20% fossil fuels; (2) an electricity mix with 75% renewables and 25% non-renewables; and (3) an electricity mix with 25% renewables and 75% non-renewables.

In Fig. 4b, Case (1) also leads to the lowest environmental CO₂ impact, regardless of power intensity, followed closely by Case (2), which has only a 5% difference in the renewable/non-renewable mix. However, Case (3) results in a higher CO₂ impact than flash calcination, regardless of power intensity.

Fig. 4. GWP potential (kg CO₂ eq/ kg activated clay) impact over the power consumption (KWh/kg) for TA and MA scenarios (L, M, H, H⁺) of (a) C1 and (b) C2 when considering three electricity cases: Case (1) country's specific electricity mix, Case (2) electricity mix: 75% renewables (G) and 25% non-renewables (NG), and Case (3) electricity mix: 75% non-renewables (NG) and 25% renewables (G).

These findings highlight that for mechanical activation to have a lower CO₂ impact than thermal activation with the given conditions, the electricity mix must include more than 25% renewable energy. This is because mechanical activation requires significantly higher power consumption, which if sourced by non-renewable energy sources such as natural gas, it will highly increase its carbon footprint. Additionally, replacing natural gas with alternative fuels for calcination and drying processes, or using 100%

renewable energy or green electricity could further reduce CO₂ emissions for both activation methods.

3.4 Energy consumption and operating cost analysis for upscaling

When considering upscaling, the total energy consumption required to activate clay using the various activation technologies evaluated in this study was calculated by summing the heat and power needed for heating, calcining, and grinding. The analysis was conducted per tonne of activated clay, as this is the relevant unit for industrial applications. Fig 5 presents a correlation between energy consumption and operating costs for TA and MA (L, M, H, H+) for both clays. Specifically, the analysis assumes electricity prices of 0.14 €/kWh and natural gas prices of 0.09 €/kWh in Brazil [33, 34] and 0.10 €/kWh and natural gas prices of 0.12 €/kWh in Denmark [35] – all values are considered as of March 2024.

Fig. 5. Correlation of energy KWh/t (electrical + thermal) with corresponding operating costs for TA and MA (L, M, H, H⁺) for (a) C1 and (b) C2 under different electricity mixes.

From Fig. 5a, the results for C1 show that thermal activation has a lower total operating cost compared to all mechanical activation scenarios, with a difference between 20 €/t (for low power MA-L) to effectively doubling the price (for high power MA-H⁺). This is due to the higher power demand associated with mechanical activation compared to thermal energy, and with the higher electricity prices. The cost of flash calcination is primarily driven by natural gas consumption. Since natural gas is relatively inexpensive in Brazil, the cost of flash calcined clay remains competitive compared to other activation technologies given the current energy mix and prices.

From Fig. 5b, the results for C2 indicate a competitive price between flash calcination and the MA-L scenario, with only a 1 €/t difference, which is rather negligible. However, the other mechanical activation scenarios (M, H, H⁺) incur higher costs, with the largest difference being 20 €/t. This is likely due to the higher cost of natural gas in Denmark compared to electricity. From an economic standpoint, this suggests that – despite having a higher energy demand – mechanical activation could be a more viable alternative to flash calcination in Denmark, especially considering its potential to reduce overall CO₂ emissions as well as any related CO₂ taxation.

3.5 Industrial considerations

After evaluating the total energy demand for TA and MA of C1 and C2 clays, it was found that energy consumption—comprising both heat and power—is higher for MA than for TA. However, MA results in a lower carbon footprint when comparing CO₂ emissions. For instance, as shown in Table 5, MA has an average 24% higher energy demand for C1 and 28% higher for C2 compared to TA, yet it achieves an average 51% reduction in CO₂ emissions for C1 and 16% for C2.

The energy demand and CO₂ emissions of clay activation are influenced by factors such as activation technology (e.g., type of calciner or mill), clay composition (kaolinite vs. smectite), moisture content (0–40%), and processing location. For example, C2 clay, rich in 2:1 mineral clay and with higher moisture content (25.3%), requires more energy for drying than C1, reducing the CO₂ advantage of mechanical activation over flash calcination.

Considering variations in clay composition, moisture content, and physical properties, the average energy consumption for flash calcination is ca. 690 kWh/t (i.e. 624 kWh/t heat, 66 kWh/t power) [10,36], while the average energy consumption for mechanical activation is ca. 658 kWh/t (450 kWh/t power, 174 kWh/t heat) [19–21]. Although the estimated total energy demands are comparable, mechanical activation has the potential to reduce CO₂ emissions by up to 70% with renewable electricity and potentially 100% with the implementation of electrical drying. In both methods, drying energy could be recovered from clinkering processes (if integrated in cement plants), and future technological developments may enable a more efficient fully electric drying for both approaches.

Table 5. Total energy demand and CO₂ emissions for TA and MA scenarios for C1 and C2.

Clay	TA		MA		
	Total energy (KWh/t)	CO ₂ emissions (kg CO ₂ /kg clay)	Total energy (KWh/t)	CO ₂ emissions (kg CO ₂ /kg clay)	
C1	419.45	0.131	L	452	0.060
			M	520	0.064
			H	587	0.066
			H+	654	0.068
			Avg.	553	0.064
C2	500	0.231	L	590	0.186
			M	658	0.190
			H	726	0.195
			H+	793	0.199
			Avg.	692	0.193

It is important to note that thermal activation has achieved a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 8–9, with soak and flash calciners commercially available [10,12], while mechanochemical activation remains at a TRL of 4–5, having been tested only at small and semi-industrial scales [19–21]. Thus, full-scale production is necessary to

validate energy transfer efficiency and demonstrate the industrial scalability and efficiency of mechanochemical activation. Key challenges in scaling up this technology include its higher electrical energy demand, equipment durability under continuous operation, and the need for comprehensive case studies to assess long-term performance and cost-effectiveness.

Despite these challenges, advancements in energy-efficient milling technologies and the growing adoption of renewable electricity present opportunities for mechanochemical activation to become a sustainable and scalable alternative to calcination, particularly for difficult-to-process clay minerals. The ultimate choice between thermal and mechanical activation will depend on the specific properties of the clays being processed, the availability of energy resources, and the environmental objectives of the operation.

4 Conclusions

A comparative Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) was conducted on thermal and mechanical clay activation of two clays sourced from Brazil and Denmark. The clays were processed under flash calcination (thermal) and high-energy milling (mechanical) using an agitated bead mill across varying power intensities from 383 to 585 KWh/t.

The analysis found that the main contributors to CO₂ emissions in thermal activation across all scenarios were the fuels used for calcination, drying, and transportation. Furthermore, the source of electricity had a significant impact on CO₂ emissions during mechanical activation. In scenarios where the electricity mix contains less than 25% renewable energy, flash calcination can result in lower CO₂ emissions than mechanical activation. However, in Brazil and Denmark, where renewable energy constitutes a significant portion of the electricity mix, mechanical activation can reduce CO₂ emissions by an average of 51% for Brazilian clay (C1) and 16% for Danish clay (C2), despite requiring a higher average energy input - 24% for C1 and 28% for C2. Under the current energy mixes and pricing structures in Brazil and Denmark, flash calcination remains the most energy-efficient, cost-effective, and scalable option.

In conclusion, the choice of activation technology for producing activated clay is heavily influenced by local energy mixes. In Brazil, where natural gas is relatively inexpensive, flash calcination is the most economical option, offering a substantial cost advantage over mechanical activation in all scenarios. In contrast, in Denmark, where electricity is cheaper than natural gas, mechanical activation—particularly in low-energy scenarios—emerges as a competitive alternative to flash calcination. Furthermore, while mechanical activation generally requires higher energy input, its potential to reduce CO₂ emissions could provide additional environmental benefits, making it a promising option in regions where sustainability goals and lower-carbon solutions are prioritized. Ultimately, the selection of activation technology depends on a combination of factors, including regional energy costs, environmental objectives, and the specific characteristics of the clay being processed.

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